

Assessing the Distributional Pattern of Dental Plaque and its Association with Cigarette Smoking.

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Abstract:

Objective: To assess the distributional pattern of dental plaque and its association with cigarette smoking in population of Pakistan.

Place and Duration of Study: This study was carried out in various dental hospitals and clinics of Lahore in a duration of 8 months from February 2018 to September 2018.

Materials and Methods: 400 willing candidates were selected and given free dental checkup in various government hospitals of Lahore. The patients visiting the outdoor department were selected to see the presence of dental plaques. Informed consent was taken from each candidate. A carefully designed proforma was used for data collection pertaining to the smoking habits. For gathering the information samples were divided into two groups on the basis of smoking habits. Smokers were classified into one group and non-smokers into another with each group having 200 candidates. Sites of dental infections were examined by risk factors i.e. habit of smoking, type of cigarette and the number of cigarettes smoked in one day.

Results: Accretion of dental plaque is most pronounced in the smokers in lower anterior lingual tooth surface and upper buccal surface in non-smokers and the accumulation of this dental plaque is thought to be highly associated with the cigarette smoking.

Conclusion: Smoking habits, number of cigarettes, type of cigarette and the duration for which a person has been smoking is found to have a correlation with accretion of dental plaque at different oral sites.

Keywords: Smoking, accretion of dental plaque, assessment, oral distribution

Introduction: Dental plaque is thought to be an intricate, metabolically interlinked, highly structured bacterial network which comprises of populated masses of microbes, streptococci analogous to streptococcus mutans, fixed in a matrix. Within two hours after the teeth have been brushed, a slender layer of fenestrated pellicle is formed on the teeth which is organic and bacteria free film. A robust connection have been found in several studies between the dental caries and soft

plaque, periodontitis and gingivitis. Although genetics along with constitutional factors play a major role in dental plaque distribution but in the occurrence of periodontal disease and accretion of dental plaques smoking has a vital role as shown in earlier studies. Association of dental plaque with smoking has been shown in multiple researches. In smoking habits the type of cigarette a person smoke and its influential role in dental plaque has been ignored. The main aim of this study was to focus on the pattern of distribution on dental plaque associated with smoking and to look for intra oral dental plaque sharing design according to habits of smoking in population of Lahore.

Materials and Methods: Patients with age between 18 to 40 years were selected and only healthy individuals were selected for the study who brush their teeth twice daily. 400 willing candidates were selected and given free dental checkup in various government hospitals of Lahore. The patients visiting the outdoor department were selected to see the presence of dental plaques. Informed consent was taken from each candidate. Ethical approval committee accepted the research topic and no objection certificate was obtained. A carefully designed proforma was used for data collection pertaining to the smoking habits. The questionnaire contained questions about the age, history, past history, family distribution of dental plaque, smoking habits and type of cigarette smoked by a person. Confidentiality of the patient was maintained with a top priority. Only healthy individuals were selected who have no history of paan, betel nuts chewing or smokeless tobacco. For gathering the information samples were divided into two groups on the basis of smoking habits. Smokers were classified into one group and non-smokers into another with each group having 200 candidates. Sites of dental infections were examined by risk factors i.e. habit of smoking, type of cigarette and the number of cigarettes smoked in one day.

Results: 200 cigarette smokers and 200 non-smokers were included in the study. Dental plaque was analyzed in 3104 different areas in the participants. 53 affected areas were seen in smokers and 48 affected areas were noticed in non-smokers. Habit of cigarette smoking was in correlation with the accretion and distribution of dental plaque. Accretion of dental plaque is most pronounced in the smokers in lower anterior lingual tooth surface and upper buccal surface in non-smokers and the accumulation of this dental plaque is thought to be highly associated with the cigarette smoking.

Time for which the person has been smoking was correlated with the division of plaque in buccal cavity. In smokers with duration of smoking greater than 14 years of smoking maximum area was noticed for the accretion of dental plaque. Individuals who have been smoking for last 5 to 9 and those with the duration of smoking less than 5 years, the incidence of accretion of dental plaque was same among them.

A person who smokes 10 or less than 10 cigarettes per day is a light smoker while a person who smokes 10 or more than 10 cigarettes per day is a heavy smoker and the plaque formation in oral cavity is linked to the number of cigarettes smoked in one day. In current research it has been found that increased number of cigarettes in one day can lead to an increased plaque deposition in oral cavity. Also, the type of cigarette used was found to have a relation with division of dental plaque. It has also been shown in this study that use of filter decreases the rate of plaque formation.

Discussion: Results of this study show the distributional pattern of dental plaque and its association with cigarette smoking. Findings found in this study correlate with the earlier studies suggesting that there is a dose dependent relationship in between formation of dental plaque and exposure to tobacco smoke when relevance of the duration and frequency of the cigarette smoke is compared. It has also been found in this study that distributional pattern of dental plaque formation is different between the smokers and

non-smoker. Habit of cigarette smoking was in correlation with the accretion and distribution of dental plaque. Accretion of dental plaque is most pronounced in the smokers in lower anterior lingual tooth surface and upper buccal surface in non-smokers and the accumulation of this dental plaque is thought to be highly associated with the cigarette smoking. The findings in this study are in correlation with the earlier studies done for US and Swedish population but varies from other ones where no relation have been found between smoking and plaque formation. Time for which the person has been smoking was correlated with the division of plaque in buccal cavity. In smokers with duration of smoking greater than 14 years about (11%) of smoking maximum area was noticed for the accretion of dental plaque. Individuals who have been smoking for last 5 to 9 and those with the duration of smoking less than 5 years (5.3%), the incidence of accretion of dental plaque was same among them. This fact have been emphasized that tissues in the oral area and other structures are badly affected by the increase in duration for which a person smokes. For persons who cannot quit smoking filtered cigarettes were introduced to decrease the harmful effects of cigarette smoke. Studies are limited in which a correlation has been shown between the smoking filtered cigarette and plaque formation in oral cavity. In our study extreme difference have been found in the level of plaque formation that occurs between the person who smokes filtered cigarette and those who smoke non filtered cigarette. Multiple factors have been postulated that increase the formation of plaque in oral cavity but decreased oxygen partial pressure in smokers favors the anaerobic bacteria and increase plaque formation. Decreased immunity in smokers leading to increased plaque formation have been shown in multiple studies. These two factors combined can accentuate the rate of plaque formation.

Conclusion: Smoking habits, number of cigarettes, type of cigarette and the duration for which a person has been smoking is found to have a correlation with accretion of dental plaque at different oral sites.

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